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European Test and Risk Assessment Strategies for Mixtures

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Deliverable D3.1

Development of CAG-specific PCR arrays

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Development of CAG-specific PCR arrays

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Introduction

The EuroMix project aims to develop an experimentally verified strategy for the risk assessment of mixtures of multiple chemicals. To refine cumulative and aggregated risk assessment the tiered mechanism-based test strategy will use in silico and in vitro tools that will be verified against in vivo data. In order to group chemicals into cumulative assessment groups (CAG) one aim of Work Package 3 was the development of CAG-specific PCR arrays to distinguish between subsets of commonly regulated genes for chemicals with different modes of action (MoA) within one CAG group. Using the concept of adverse outcome pathways (AOPs) the endpoints in EuroMix (liver toxicity, developmental toxicity and endocrine effects) were exemplarily aligned with selected CAGs by EFSA resulting in three different AOPs: AOP for liver steatosis, AOP for craniofacial skeletal malformations and AOP for endocrine (anti-androgenic) effects.

PCR array for AOP leading to liver steatosis

A PCR array consisting of 69 human marker genes for liver steatosis was developed. The selection of genes was based on already existing in vitro (HepaRG cells) and in vivo (rat) data on steatosis by BfR, information from the AOP on steatosis, and gene lists from commercial PCR arrays. In Task 3.3 the PCR array will help to demonstrate how chemicals in one CAG group can be sub-grouped according to different MoA based on gene regulation patterns.

No	Gene symbol	Gene name
1	ACACA	Acetyl-CoA carboxylase alpha
2	ACOX1 (AOX)	Acyl-CoA oxidase 1, palmitoyl
3	ADH1A	Alcohol dehydrogenase 1A (class I), alpha polypeptide
4	ADK	Adenosine kinase
5	ALDH2	Aldehyde dehydrogenase 2 family (mitochondrial)
6	AQP2	Aquaporin 2
7	ATP8B1	ATPase, aminophospholipid transporter, class I, type 8B, member 1
8	CCL5	Chemokine (C-C motif) ligand 5
9	CD36 (FAT)	CD36 molecule (thrombospondin receptor) (fatty acid translocase)
10	CEBPD	CCAAT/enhancer binding protein (C/EBP), delta
11	CES2	Carboxylesterase 2
12	CHREBP (MLXIPL)	Carbohydrate response element binding protein (MLX interacting protein-like)
13	COMT	Catechol-O-methyltransferase
14	CYBB (NOX2)	Cytochrome b-245, beta polypeptide
15	CYP1A2	Cytochrome P450 family 1 subfamily A member 2
16	CYP1B1	Cytochrome P450 family 1 subfamily B member 1
17	CYP2A6	Cytochrome P450 family 2 subfamily A member 6

No	Gene symbol	Gene name
18	CYP2B6	Cytochrome P450 family 2 subfamily B member 6
19	CYP2C19	Cytochrome P450 family 2 subfamily C member 19
20	CYP2C9	Cytochrome P450 family 2 subfamily C member 9
21	CYP2D6	Cytochrome P450 family 2 subfamily D member 6
22	CYP2E1	Cytochrome P450 family 2 subfamily E member 1
23	CYP3A4	Cytochrome P450 family 3 subfamily A member 4
24	CYP3A5	Cytochrome P450 family 3 subfamily A member 5
25	CYP3A7	Cytochrome P450 family 3 subfamily A member 7
26	CYP7A1	Cytochrome P450 family 7 subfamily A member 1
27	CYP7B1	Cytochrome P450 family 7 subfamily B member 1
28	DNM1	Dynamin 1
29	ENO1	Enolase 1, (alpha)
30	FAS (TNFRSF6)	Fas cell surface death receptor
31	FASN	Fatty acid synthase
32	FBXO32	F-box protein 32
33	G6PC	Glucose-6-phosphatase, catalytic subunit
34	G6PD	Glucose-6-phosphate dehydrogenase
35	GPD1	Glycerol-3-phosphate dehydrogenase 1
36	HAAO	3-Hydroxyanthranilate 3,4-dioxygenase
37	HADHB	Hydroxyacyl-CoA dehydrogenase/3-ketoacyl-CoA thiolase/enoyl-CoA hydratase (trifunctional protein), beta subunit
38	IL6	Interleukin 6
39	INSIG1	Insulin induced gene 1
40	JUN	Jun proto-oncogene
41	KHK	Ketohexokinase
42	LMNA	Lamin A/C
43	LPL	Lipoprotein lipase
44	LY6D	Lymphocyte antigen 6 complex, locus D
45	MAPK8 (JNK1)	Mitogen-activated protein kinase 8
46	MSMO1 (SC4mol)	Methylsterol monooxygenase 1
47	MTTP	Microsomal triglyceride transfer protein
48	NOS2	Nitric oxide synthase 2
49	NQO1	NAD(P)H dehydrogenase, quinone 1
50	NR0B2 (SHP)	Nuclear receptor subfamily 0 group B member 2
51	PCCA	Propionyl-CoA carboxylase alpha subunit
52	PK4	Pyruvate dehydrogenase kinase, isozyme 4
53	PNPLA3	Patatin like phospholipase domain containing 3
54	POR	P450 (cytochrome) oxidoreductase
55	PPARA	Peroxisome proliferator-activated receptor alpha
56	PPARGC1A	Peroxisome proliferator-activated receptor gamma, coactivator 1 alpha
57	RETN	Resistin
58	RGCC	Regulator of cell cycle
59	SCD	Stearoyl-CoA desaturase (delta-9-desaturase)
60	SLCO1A4	Solute carrier organic anion transporter family member 4A1
61	SREBF1 (SREBP-1c)	Sterol regulatory element binding transcription factor 1 (sterol response element binding protein 1c)
62	STBD1	Starch binding domain 1
63	SULT1B1	Sulfotransferase family 1B member 1
64	SULT1C2	Sulfotransferase family 1C member 2
65	SYT1	Synaptotagmin 1
66	TFF3	Trefoil factor 3

No	Gene symbol	Gene name
67	TUBB2B	Tubulin beta 2B class IIb
68	UGT2B7	UDP glucuronosyltransferase 2 family, polypeptide B7
69	VCP	Valosin containing protein

PCR array for AOP leading to craniofacial skeletal malformations

This list is based on human genes related to cleft palate (1. Funato 2017); mouse/rat and zebrafish orthologs are provided in view of the used *in vitro* models, but homologs/orthologs were not clear in all cases (marked with ?). In some cases, multiple orthologs were retrieved. The list is completed with key genes derived from molecular pathways/networks described by Hutson 2017 (2) and Hu 2015 (3) for cleft palate in mouse and Mork (4) for zebrafish midline malformations. Functions are derived from references 2, 3, and 4. Two additional Hox genes are from a reference provided by Elena Menegola (5) and one Loxl gene is derived from Van Boxtel (6).

No	Gene symbol		Pathway	Function	Ref
	Mouse/rat	Zebrafish			
1	Alx1	alx1	AhR		1
2	Alx3	alx3	AhR		1
3	Alx4	alx4a,alx4b	AhR		1
4	Arnt	arnt	AhR		1
5	Bmp2	bmp2b	AhR	signaling molecule	1,2
6	Bmp4	bmp4	AhR	signaling molecule	1,2
7	Ctnnb1	ctnnb1	RA	signaling molecule [b-catenin]	3
8	Dlx5	dlx5a	RA	intermediate molecule	1,2
9	Efnb1	efnb1	AhR	signaling molecule	1,2
10	Bmpr1a	bmpr1a, bmp1aa, bmp1ab	AhR	intermediate molecule	2
11	c-Myc	c-myc	AhR	intermediate molecule	2
12	c-jun	c-jun	RA	signaling molecule	3
13	Crispld2	crispld2	Probably RA	midline malf mutant	4
14	Egf	egf	AhR	signaling molecule	2
15	Egfr	egfr(5)	AhR	intermediate molecule	2
16	Erk	erk	AhR	intermediate molecule	2
17	Faf1	faf1	RA	midline malf mutant	4
18	Fgf1	fgf1a,fgf1b	RA	signaling molecule	1,3
19	Fgf2	fgf2	RA	signaling molecule	1,3
20	Fgf7	fgf7	AhR	signaling molecule	2
21	Fgf8	fgf8a	RA	signaling molecule	1,3
22	Fgf10	fgf10a	AhR	signaling molecule, midline malf mutant	1,2,3,4
23	Fgf17	fgf17	RA	signaling molecule	1,3
24	Fgf15/Fgf19 (m/r)	fgf19	RA	signaling molecule	1,3
25	Fgfr2b?	?	AhR	intermediate molecule	2
26	Gli1	gli1	AhR	intermediate molecule	
27	Gnrh1	?			1
28	Gsk-3b	gsk3b	RA	signaling molecule	3
29	Hoxa2	hoxa2b	RA		1,5

No	Gene symbol		Pathway	Function	Ref
	Mouse/rat	Zebrafish			
30	Hoxa3	hoxa3a	RA		5
31	Hoxd4	hoxd4a	RA		5
32	Irf6	irf6	RA	midline malf mutant	1,4
33	Lef-1	lef1	RA		3
34	Lhx8	lhx8a	RA	signaling molecule	1
35	Loxl3	lox13a,lox13b	Lox	signaling molecule, ECM shaping	6
36	MAPK	mapk	AhR	intermediate molecule	2
37	Med25	med25	AhR	midline malf mutant	4
38	Mir140	mir140	AhR	midline malf mutant	4
39	Mmp9	mmp9	AhR	signaling molecule	1,2
40	Msx1	msxe	RA	intermediate molecule	1,2
41	Msx2	msxd	RA		1
42	Nog	nog1,nog3	AhR	signaling molecule	1,2
43	Pdgfra	pdgfra	AhR	midline malf mutant	4
44	Pi3k	pi3k	AhR	intermediate molecule	2
45	Ptc1/Ptch1	ptch1	AhR	intermediate molecule	2
46	PTEN	pten, ptena, ptenb	AhR	intermediate molecule	2
47	Rac1	rac1(8)	RA	signaling molecule	
48	Runx2	runx2a	AhR	midline malformation	1
49	Shh	shha,shhb	RA	signaling molecule	1,2,3
50	Smad3	smad3b	AhR	intermediate molecule	1,2
51	Smad4	zmp:0000000768	AhR	intermediate molecule	1,2
52	Smad5	smad5	AhR	intermediate molecule	4
53	Smo	smo	AhR	intermediate molecule	2
54	Sox9	sox9a	AhR		1
55	Spry4	spry4	Probably RA	signaling molecule	1,3
56	Tbx1	tbx1	RA		1
57	Tbx22	tbx22			1
58	Tgfa	tgfa			1
59	Tgfb2	tgfb2	RA	midline malf mutant	1,4
60	Tgfb3	tgfb3	RA/AhR	signaling molecule, midline malf mutant	1,2
61	Tgfbr1	tgfbr1a, tgfbr1b	RA/AhR	intermediate molecule	2
62	Tgfbr2	tgfbr2	RA/AhR	intermediate molecule	2
63	Twist1	twist1a,twist1b	RA		1
64	Whsc1	whsc1	RA		1
65	Wnt3	wnt3	RA	signaling molecule	1
66	Wnt5a	wnt5a	RA	signaling molecule	1
67	Wnt7a	wnt7aa	RA	signaling molecule	1
68	Wwp2	wwp2	AhR	midline malf mutant	4

PCR array for AOP leading to receptor mediated estrogenic and/or anti-androgenic effects

This list is based on a quick search in literature focusing first on human, rat and zebrafish tissues that preferably express either the estrogen (ER) or androgen receptor (AR), followed by a search for genes that were specifically regulated in these tissues or derived cell lines from these tissues when exposed to known modulators of these receptors.

The identified target genes and tissues are an option for additional AOP event analysis in the in vivo tests with zebrafish and rat. At least we should consider to store these tissues after the in vivo tests, for such additional qPCR analysis.

No	Gene symbol			Receptor and Tissue
	Human	Rat	Zebrafish	
1	pS2			ER breast
2	C-Myc			ER breast
3	Cathepsin D			ER breast
4	Cyclic D1			ER breast
5	PR			ER breast
6	SET8			ER prostate
7	SIRT1Y			ER prostate
8	PSA			AR prostate
9	TMPRSS2			AR prostate
10	ORM1			AR prostate
11	FKBP51			AR prostate
12		AR		ER prostate
13		ER alpha		ER prostate
14		RAR		ER prostate
15		TGF beta		ER prostate
16		Hox-13		ER prostate
17		Nkx3.1		ER prostate
18		PBP C3		AR prostate
19		TRPM-2		AR prostate
20		ODC		AR prostate
21		IGF-1		AR prostate
22		InsI3		AR testis
23			vtg1	ER liver
24			vtg3	ER liver
25			esr1	ER liver
26			cpn1	ER liver
27			eif4e1b	ER liver
28			cyp11a1	ER liver
29			zp3	ER liver
30			f2	ER liver
31			tropomyosin	AR gonads
32			nr5a1	AR gonads
33			azan1	AR gonads